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Robust Hydropower Planning Balances Energy Generation, Carbon Emissions and Sediment Connectivity in the Mekong River Basin

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Key Points:

- We identify optimal dam portfolios which balance hydropower expansion, sediment supply disruption, and GHG emissions in the Mekong
- We extracted optimal portfolios under multiple state-of-the-world configurations, to extract robust indicators of project attractiveness
- Results suggest that near-term dam development should focus more on the upper Mekong, compared to the lower Mekong and its tributaries

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Abstract We present a framework for strategic dam planning under uncertainty, which includes GHG emissions mitigation as a novel objective. We focus on the Mekong River Basin, a fast-developing region heavily relying on river-derived ecosystem services. We employ a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm to identify strategic dam portfolios for different hydropower expansion targets, using process-related and statistical models to derive indicators of sediment supply disruption and GHG emissions. We introduce a robust optimization approach that explores variations in optimal portfolio compositions for more than 5,000 state-of-the-world configurations, regarding sediment origins and trapping and GHG emissions. Thus, we can rank dam projects' attractiveness based on their frequency of inclusion in optimal portfolios and explore how uncertainty affects these rankings. Our results suggest that developing dams in the upper Mekong would be a more robust option for near-term development than, for example, the lower Mekong and its tributaries, for both environmental and energy objectives. Our work presents a novel approach to better understand the basin-scale cumulative impacts of dam development in high-uncertainty, data-scarce contexts like the Mekong Basin.

Plain Language Summary Hydropower is considered an important energy source to meet many climate mitigation targets. Its negative impacts are however often underestimated, including the emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) from reservoirs. This study introduces a framework for planning dams strategically in the Mekong River Basin, a region heavily dependent on river-related services. The framework considers uncertainties and incorporates greenhouse gas emissions mitigation and sediment transport disruption as new objectives. Using a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm, the research identifies optimal dam portfolios for different hydropower expansion goals. To consider uncertainties in the results, the analysis employs a robust optimization approach to assess over 5,000 state-of-the-world configurations. Results indicate that developing dams in the upper Mekong is a more robust option for both environmental and energy goals in the near term. These conclusions showcase the approach's usefulness in understanding dams' cumulative impacts in data-scarce and uncertain contexts like the Mekong Basin.

1. Introduction

Strategic planning can help reconcile the environmental and social impacts of dams, their economic benefits, and their influence on the global climate. Strategic planning uses numerical models to comparatively analyze different combinations of dam sites, selecting those that result in the best trade-offs among multiple conflicting objectives. This approach has been demonstrated to outperform the current dam development paradigm, where dams are developed site-by-site according to mostly economic criteria (Almeida et al., 2022; Flecker et al., 2022; Grill et al., 2019; Hurford, McCartney, et al., 2020; Opperman et al., 2017; Schmitt et al., 2021; Thieme et al., 2021).

The inclusion of externalities as additional objectives in strategic dam planning allows for the identification of optimal trade-offs between economic and social objectives and environmental impacts. Objectives like food security, fish migration, and sediment connectivity have been integrated into decision-making frameworks to support the identification of sustainable dam portfolios in large and data-scarce environments (Almeida et al., 2019; Schmitt, Bizzi, et al., 2019; Ziv et al., 2012).

There is mounting evidence that dammed reservoirs can emit significant amounts of greenhouse gases (GHG), on top of other local and basin-wide impacts. Recent work highlighted how emissions emitted directly and indirectly

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as a consequence of reservoir construction and operations are often non-negligible, and sometimes even comparable to traditional fossil fuel-fired power plants (Calamita et al., 2021; Edenhofer, 2015; Prairie et al., 2018; Räsänen et al., 2018; Scherer & Pfister, 2016).

GHG emissions from dams (mainly CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) are predominantly driven by decaying organic matter in the reservoir, either flooded during filling, delivered from the river catchment via tributaries and runoff, or produced in the impoundment (algae and aquatic plants) (Prairie et al., 2018). Although most hydropower plants have a carbon intensity (i.e., total GHG emissions per unit of produced electricity) comparable to other types of renewable energy, certain conditions could lead to values an order of magnitude higher (Scherer & Pfister, 2016). These conditions are, among others, a large flooded area, an elevated organic matter content in the flooded area and inflow, high water temperature, and an anoxic bottom layer, which are all typically featured in low-latitude reservoirs (Demarty & Bastien, 2011; Teodoru et al., 2012). While the average carbon intensity of global hydropower has been identified as around 20 kg CO₂ eq/MWh, some hydropower projects have emissions on the same order of magnitude as gas and oil-fired power plants (100–1,000 kg CO₂ eq/MWh) (NREL, 2021; Räsänen et al., 2018).

Most of the remaining hydropower potential is located in the world's large tropical and subtropical rivers (Grill et al., 2019; World Commission on Dams, 2000). Large-scale hydropower development plans in these basins are therefore at risk of emitting significant amounts of GHG, on top of elevated risks of ecosystem and ecosystem services degradation (Latrubesse et al., 2017). One of the most significant dam development hotspots is the Mekong River, a transboundary river basin in South-East Asia that is among the 10 largest river systems in the world. The Mekong River system supports the largest freshwater fishery in the world and one of the largest rice production agricultural districts (MRC (Mekong River Commission), 2018). Further, its unique aquatic biodiversity is second only to the Amazon basin (Oberdorff et al., 1995). The Mekong's high sediment transport rate allows a steady supply of nutrients that nurtures the river's ecological hotspots and fertile downstream floodplains, and the delivery of material to the Mekong Delta is vital to its stability and habitability (G. Kondolf et al., 2022; Paul, 2019; Schmitt et al., 2018a, 2021).

Leveraging the Mekong Basin's large hydropower potential, estimated at 268,000 GWh per year, can conflict with maintaining the Mekong's panoply of ecosystem services. More than half of the potential dam sites have been developed based on a site-by-site rather than an integrated whole-basin approach, often locking-in ecological and socio-environmental problems that would have been avoidable (Schmitt et al., 2018a).

Previous studies have demonstrated that strategic, coordinated planning and operation of reservoirs can help balance trade-offs between energy production and environmental concerns in the Mekong, considering fish biodiversity (Orr et al., 2012; Ziv et al., 2012), sediment trapping and connectivity (G. M. Kondolf, Rubin, & Minear, 2014; Schmitt et al., 2018a; Wild & Loucks, 2014), and hydrological impacts (Hecht et al., 2019). Because of their location, individual dams in the Mekong have been shown to potentially emit more GHG per unit of electricity than fossil fuel plants (Räsänen et al., 2018). Thus, for a given energy target, strategic planning can help select dam portfolios generating the least GHG carbon intensities, and thus global impacts, as well as lessen local environmental impacts on rivers. However, these opportunities have not yet been explored for the Mekong.

Additionally, no previous studies in the Mekong account for and quantify how robust results are in the light of our often rudimentary understanding of river processes in the basin. This is especially true for processes like GHG emissions from reservoirs due to challenges collecting relevant data, especially for proposed projects, and a lack of scientific consensus on how to measure them (Hurford, Harou, et al., 2020).

Building on the work of Schmitt, Bizzi, et al. (2019) and Almeida et al. (2019), this paper presents the strategic optimization of dam portfolios for the Mekong considering GHG emissions and sediment trapping based on a robust and bottom-up approach that uses available information in a stochastic approach. This approach identifies the most relevant drivers of uncertainty and robust decisions about future dam portfolios, that is, which decisions would be similar even if existing data are not accurate and which decisions would require more data to result in desirable outcomes.

The task of strategic hydropower planning requires robust approaches, especially when considering processes characterized by high uncertainty like hydropower GHG emissions. Our work is intended to not only inform decision-making in the Mekong, but also highlight how new numerical approaches can support robust strategic hydropower planning even in poorly monitored river basins and under large uncertainty.

2. Case Study

The 4,909-km-long Mekong River is the eighth-largest river system in the world and the longest in South-East Asia (Winemiller et al., 2016). It originates in the Tibetan Plateau and flows southward towards the South China Sea. The Mekong Basin covers 790,000 km², shared between six countries: China (21% of the basin), Myanmar (3%), Laos (25%), Thailand (23%), Cambodia (20%), and Vietnam (8%). The Mekong River Basin (MRB) is traditionally divided between the Upper Mekong (also known as Lancang) and Lower Mekong River Basin, delineated by the border between China and Laos and Thailand (Campbell, 2009). The terminus of the Mekong is the Mekong Delta, an area of exceptional agricultural productivity, which supports 17 million inhabitants and produces 7%–10% of all rice traded internationally (Molle et al., 2012).

The Mekong basin has a large potential for hydropower expansion. Fifty-six dams are already constructed or in construction in the basin, which produces around 138,000 GWh/year (Schmitt, Bizzi, et al., 2019). Most existing dams are located in the Lancang region and lower Mekong tributaries, with the exception of the 1,260-MW Xayaburi Dam in Thailand. Sixty-eight new candidates have been identified (Schmitt, Bizzi, et al., 2019), which could generate an additional 130,000 GWh/year (Figure 1a). These planned projects consist of large mainstream dams on the lower Mekong River, projects on the Lancang nested between existing dams and smaller dams on the tributaries.

Sediment transport along the Mekong and its tributaries is crucial for the biophysical functioning of this river basin. Sediment transport to the Mekong Delta has been estimated to be around 140–160 million metric tons per year (Mt/year) (Milliman & Meade, 1983). This sediment load originates from different parts of the basin. While data on sediment origins in the basins are scarce, it has been estimated that, before dam construction, around 50% of the total sediment load originated in the Upper MRB alone (G. M. Kondolf, Rubin, & Minear, 2014). The rest of the sediment originated mostly from the highlands south of the border with China and several major tributaries in the lower Mekong (Bravard et al., 2014). Most dams, and particularly large dams like the major reservoir projects on the Lancang, trap some part of the incoming sediment load (G. M. Kondolf, Gao, et al., 2014; G. M. Kondolf, Rubin, & Minear, 2014; Schmitt, Bizzi, et al., 2019). As a result, modeling and remote sensing studies indicate that the sediment load of the Mekong has already been reduced to more than half of its original load. If all dams were built, a 96% reduction of sediment delivery to the delta is expected (G. M. Kondolf, Rubin, & Minear, 2014; Schmitt, Bizzi, et al., 2019). Together with additional reductions due to sand mining, rising sea levels, shifting monsoon patterns, natural subsidence, and loss of nature-based coastal protection, the sediment starvation would lead to a loss of around 90% of the Mekong Delta by 2100, if no measures are implemented to avoid such fate (G. Kondolf et al., 2022; Schmitt et al., 2017). While multiple options for reservoir sediment management are available, such as repeated drawdown sediment flushing operations, (G. M. Kondolf, Gao, et al., 2014) none are known and planned for existing and future projects on the Mekong (Wild et al., 2016).

Sediment trapping has relevant regional impacts, but dams also have implications for the global climate. Some hydropower projects in the Mekong consist of lowland, mainstream dams which tend to have significant carbon emissions due to their larger reservoir areas and location in often densely vegetated tropical regions with high biomass content (Räsänen et al., 2018). GHG emissions from downstream reservoirs like the lower-basin Sambor dam may even possess a carbon intensity comparable to fossil fuel power plants (Räsänen et al., 2018).

3. Materials and Methods

Solving trade-offs between the benefits of dams (hydropower generation) and ecosystem impacts (sediment trapping and greenhouse gas emissions) requires a strategic approach to dam siting which considers and incorporates uncertainties into its decision-making framework. We herein propose a two-step approach routed robust decision analysis:

1. Baseline scenarios. We use a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm coupled to models for hydropower generation, reservoir GHG emissions, and sediment delivery to the Mekong Delta (one model, or objective function, for each objective). In this step, all models for environmental impacts are run using central estimates for relevant parameters. This algorithm allows us to identify an optimal sequence of dam sites. This sequence yields optimal trade-offs between the three considered objectives as hydropower expands in the basin.
2. Portfolio robustness. By including uncertainty in the objective functions, we analyze the robustness of the optimal development sequence. If, for instance, a small change in model parameters would result in the

Figure 1. Geography of the Mekong River Basin, siting of the existing and possible major dams and relative cumulative carbon emissions and intensity. The marker size in figure (a) indicates the mean annual hydropower generation (GWh/year). Gray and red markers identify dams already existing/in construction and planned/proposed, respectively. A black dot inside the marker denotes mainstream dams. Figure (b) shows the equivalent GHG emissions of the planned projects. Marker color indicates the reservoir's total carbon dioxide equivalent emissions (kg CO₂ eq/year), and globe sizes indicate carbon intensity (kg CO₂ eq/MWh). Data on carbon intensity for traditional non-renewable Power Plants (PP) is also reported (data from NREL (2021)). The average and interquartile ranges (Q1 and Q3) for carbon intensity are shown for coal, oil and gas power plants.

identification of a very different development scenario, our recommendations for how to expand hydropower with the least impact would not be robust to uncertainty. As a result, we can identify a set of robust recommendations that will likely lead to good trade-offs between the three objectives, even under uncertainty.

3.1. Dam Database

Deriving a database of existing and potential dam sites constitutes the first step in strategic hydropower planning (Almeida et al., 2022). We use the dam database compiled by Schmitt, Bizzi, et al. (2019) from publicly available data (International Rivers, 2014; Mekong, 2014; MRC (Mekong River Commission), 2014; Räsänen et al., 2017). The database omits smaller hydropower dams and irrigation weirs and barriers, and reports mean annual inflow

(m³/year), total storage, (m³), annual generation (GWh/year), and the development status and expected operation date for each dam site. As mentioned above, this database indicates that 56 dams are operational, and further 68 dam sites have been identified for future development.

3.2. Extracting Optimal Development Sequences

Dam development sequences, both for the baseline and robust analysis, are obtained using the Borg multi-objective evolutionary algorithm (Hadka & Reed, 2013) and post-processing its results. BORG solves a decision-making problem of the form:

$$\min_U(-J_1(U), -J_2(U), J_3(U)) \quad (1)$$

in which J_1 is the indicator for sediment supply to the delta (Mt/year), J_2 is the indicator for hydropower production (GWh/year), J_3 is the indicator for GHG emissions from reservoirs (kg CO₂eq/day). As BORG tries to minimize the objectives, J_1 and J_2 are reported with a minus sign. The calculation of these objectives is described below. $U = u_1 \dots u_{68}$ denotes the decision vector, composed of 68 binary decision variables u , one for each potential dam site, which indicates whether the dam is included in the portfolio or not. The Borg algorithm explores the decision space and iteratively extracts increasingly refined Pareto fronts composed by Pareto Optimal (PO) portfolios, that is, portfolios with optimal trade-offs between the three objectives, via genetic selection procedures. As detailed in other papers (Flecker et al., 2022; Schmitt, Bizzi, et al., 2019; Ziv et al., 2012), optimal dam portfolios can be post-processed to analyze which level of hydropower generation (i.e., which future demand) would likely present a strategic choice for each dam.

3.3. Indicator for Hydropower Production

The annual hydropower generation J_1 of a specific portfolio P is calculated as the sum of $W(d)$, the tabulated mean annual generation of all dams d in that portfolio.

$$J_1(P) = \sum_{d \in P} W(d) \quad (2)$$

3.4. Indicator for Sediment Supply

To calculate the effects on the annual sediment supply for a portfolio of dams, we follow the approach described in Schmitt, Bizzi, et al. (2019). We thus use a simplified version of the CASCADE sediment connectivity model (Bizzi et al., 2021; Schmitt, 2016; Schmitt et al., 2018b; Tangi et al., 2019, 2022) to quantify how different combinations of dam sites would alter sediment supply to the Mekong Delta.

Some of the key parameters for CASCADE are, first, where sediment originates in the basin, and how much sediment is thus potentially transported in different locations of the river network. Second, CASCADE requires estimates of how much sediment will be trapped in each dam. For the former, our analysis is based on estimates from G. M. Kondolf, Rubin, and Minear (2014), who partitioned the river basin into nine regions and a specific value of catchment sediment yield (t/km²/year) to each. We then calculate the direct drainage area for each reach in the CASCADE's river network (km²). Based on that area, and the reach location, the model determines how much sediment enters that reach and is subsequently routed downstream towards the Mekong Delta.

CASCADE also contains a component to calculate sediment trapping in single dams and cumulative impacts, if multiple dams are built in a river network. If a dam is built, part of the incoming sediment is trapped and downstream sediment transport is reduced. Sediment trapping is derived using the Brune formula (Brune, 1953), an empirical formula depending on the hydraulic residence time of each dam's reservoir (G. M. Kondolf, Rubin, & Minear, 2014; Vörösmarty et al., 2003).

3.5. Indicators for GHG Emissions

GHG emissions for each dam portfolio are defined as the sum of the mean annual values of the life-cycle total net GHG emissions (hereby GHG emissions) of all included dams:

$$J_3(P) = \sum_{d \in P} GHG_{net,tot}(d) \quad (3)$$

Where $GHG_{net,tot}(d)$ is the life-cycle total net CO₂-equivalent emissions (kg CO₂ eq/year). Net emissions also consider the emissions of the pre-flood landscape, and whether the area was previously a carbon sink (e.g., soils, forests, agricultural lands) or a carbon source (e.g., rivers, lakes, peatlands, swamps) (Demarty & Bastien, 2011; Song et al., 2018). There are few field measurements of GHG emissions in the region, which could be used to estimate GHG emissions of current and future dams. We thus estimate GHG emissions (kg CO₂ eq/year) from each dam reservoir using an empirical formula that accounts for the major GHG emitting processes in reservoirs, like diffusion of dissolved CO₂ and CH₄ at the air-water interface, CH₄ bubble emissions, or degassing at turbines and spillways or downstream of the dam. We employed a database of GHG fluxes for existing tropical and subtropical reservoirs Deemer et al. (2016) and used the procedure in Almeida et al. (2019) to estimate emissions for future reservoirs. Herein, we consider only CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes, as N₂O fluxes generally represent less than 5% of the total gross CO₂eq emissions from reservoirs. The total GHG emissions from each dam reservoir are computed as follows:

$$GHG_{net,tot}(d) = A(d) \times (net_{CO_2} * F_{CO_2}(d) + net_{CH_4} * F_{CH_4}(d) * GWP_{CH_4}) (1 + R_{downstream}) \quad (4)$$

where $GHG_{net,tot}(d)$ is the total net GHG flux (kg CO₂eq/day) for each dam (d), $F_{CO_2}(d)$ and $F_{CH_4}(d)$ are respectively the gross CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes (kg/km²/day), and A(d) is the reservoir flooded area (km²) (Deemer et al., 2016). To convert CH₄ emissions into CO₂eq emissions, the net methane flux was multiplied by a factor GWP_{CH_4} equal to 34 kg CO₂eq/kg CH₄, which is the conversion factor for the global warming potential of methane over 100-year time horizon (Myhre et al., 2013). Since $F_{CO_2}(d)$ and $F_{CH_4}(d)$ refer to gross fluxes, we converted these values to net GHG emissions, in order to account only for the net (anthropogenic) change associated with reservoir creation. Correction factors were applied according to the findings of Prairie et al. (2018). In the absence of land cover information, the authors suggested conservatively assuming that 75% of the gross CO₂ emissions and 10% of the gross CH₄ emissions also existed in the pre-impoundment conditions. Hence, correction factors netCO₂ and netCH₄ were put equal to 0.25 and 0.90, respectively. Since turbine intakes often draw methane-rich bottom waters, an extra amount of CH₄ is emitted downstream of the dam. To account for this, a multiplier factor of $(1 + R_{downstream})$ was applied to the calculation, where $R_{downstream}$ is a constant representing the ratio of downstream emissions to reservoir-surface emissions (both expressed in terms of netCO₂), estimated to be 17% (Forsberg et al., 2017).

A useful metric to evaluate the greenhouse gas emission potential of the energy generated in power plants is the Carbon Intensity (CI) (kg CO₂eq/MWh) defined as:

$$CI(d) = \frac{GHG_{net,tot}(d)}{HPP_{day,tot}(d)} + CI_{construction} \quad (5)$$

where $HPP_{day,tot}(d)$ is the total hydropower production of a given dam over a day (MWh/day) and $CI_{construction}$ is a constant representing the Carbon Intensity associated with construction and infrastructure of hydropower dams, estimated to be equal to 19 kg CO₂eq/MWh for a 100-year time horizon (Edenhofer et al., 2011).

To estimate uncertainty ranges, GHG fluxes data reported (Deemer et al., 2016) were re-sampled through a bootstrapping procedure with equal probability, combined, and summed 10,000 times. In this way, 10,000 values of total net GHG emissions (kg CO₂e/day) were obtained for each dam. Lastly, the Carbon Intensity value used in the average scenario for each dam was computed as the average over the 10,000 values.

Figure 1b shows total GHG emissions and the carbon intensity of the planned reservoirs. Both total emissions and carbon intensity increase for more downstream dams, as the ratio of reservoir flooded area to hydropower generation increases. Small reservoirs on downstream tributaries like the 3S and Tonle Sap have the highest CI, while upstream dams on the Upper MRC report the lowest values. While large downstream reservoirs on the mainstream Mekong have the largest carbon emissions, their carbon intensity is relatively contained due to their high hydropower production. As shown, some planned reservoirs, especially projects in the lower MRB, present an average CI higher than the average CI of non-renewable power plants reported in literature (NREL, 2021).

3.6. Deriving Robust Strategies for Dam Development

The robustness of the strategic planning approach was evaluated using 5120 sets of possible input parameters for each of the two environmental objective functions. We then used BORG to identify Pareto optimal (PO) dam portfolios for each set of input parameters. We determined the probability with which a dam is included in each set of PO dam portfolios. Comparing this probability for each dam between the 5120 independent sets of PO dam portfolios allowed inferring how robust the selection of a certain dam was according to uncertainty.

The 5120 sets of model parameters were derived using a Sobol sampling approach (Sobol', 1967) that considered uncertainty in 18 key parameters. First, we considered uncertainty in sediment origins. For that, we varied baseline sediment yield estimated by G. M. Kondolf, Rubin, and Minear (2014) for 7 geomorphic provinces between 0.2 and 2 times the baseline value. 2 provinces out of 9 identified by G. M. Kondolf, Rubin, and Minear (2014) had zero net sediment yield and are therefore not considered.

Second, we considered the uncertainty related to dam impacts. Note that ideally the uncertainty related to each dam would have been analyzed independently. However, this was computationally unfeasible, as it would have required a Sobol sequence of hundreds of thousands of sets to guarantee a reasonable and well-sampled representation of all possible combinations of independent parameters. For both GHG and sediment objectives, we thus determined groups of dams with similar characteristics and varied parameters for those groups rather than for each dam, which allowed us to drastically reduce the size of the Sobol set.

Regarding GHG emissions, we grouped dams into five groups. For that, we first determined the 2.5th percentile and the 97.5th percentile of greenhouse gas emissions from each dam and calculated the 2.5–95 percentile range. We then classified dams into five groups according to their percentile range. Groups were derived using Jenks' natural breaks approach (Jenks, 1967). In each Sobol set, the emissions from all dams in each group were then perturbed by the same percentage. For example, in set 1, the GHG emissions of all dams with the lowest percentile range were increased by 10%, while the emissions of dams in the highest percentile range were decreased by 5%. This approach was based on the assumption that dams with similarly estimated spreads in their GHG emissions are also subject to comparable levels of uncertainty.

Regarding sediment trapping, each Sobol set modified the trapping efficiency for all dams between 0.5 and 1.5 of a dam's respective baseline value to represent uncertainty in the Brune equation. Thus, the trapping efficiency for all dams increased and decreased in unison between all sets. Then, we evaluated uncertainty in sediment trapping related to the adaptation of sediment management strategies. For that, we decided to focus on drawdown sediment flushing operations, known to be among the most efficient and cost-effective options for sediment management (G. M. Kondolf, Gao, et al., 2014). We initially determined if sediment flushing could at all be effective in a dam site. According to (G. M. Kondolf, Gao, et al., 2014) flushing is only practically feasible if reservoir gross storage (m^3) does not exceed 4% of the mean annual inflow ($m^3/year$). As many dams in the Mekong are built without bottom outlets, we also did not consider flushing in existing dams. For all those dams (existing, or not meeting the 4% criteria), we did not consider any additional uncertainty. We then group the remaining dams per country, assuming that policies in each of the basin's five countries with hydropower potential (note that Myanmar does not have any dam sites) will control if sediment management strategies are implemented in a dam. Each Sobol set then varied the flushing efficiency between 0.1 and 1.

All uncertainties were independent of one another and the Sobol set presented a uniform sampling between the maximum and minimum values for each parameter.

To analyze the results, we classified the dam sequences into 14 levels based on their cumulative hydropower generation (from 1.3 to 2.7×10^5 GWh/year, discretized at 0.1×10^5 GWh/year).

For each level, we computed the probability of inclusion of each dam as:

$$Pr_{d,l} = \frac{N_{P_r}(d \in P_r)}{N_{P_r}} \quad (6)$$

where N_{P_r} is the number of PO portfolios whose cumulative production (the objective $J_1(P)$) falls inside the range r , and $N_{P_r}(d \in P_r)$ is the number of PO portfolios inside r which include dam d .

For each dam, we first applied the formula in Equation 6 for all PO portfolios across all the 5120 scenarios to calculate the average probability of inclusion. Then, we applied the formula to each one of the 5120 scenarios independently and then compared the resulting statistics, to measure instead how the probability of inclusion varies across scenarios.

4. Results

4.1. Pareto Optimal Portfolios for the Average Scenario

Figure 2a displays the three-objective Pareto frontier, derived using central estimates for sediment yield, sediment trapping, and GHG emissions. Each dot in panel 2a indicates a different dam portfolio, that is, a different spatial configuration of dam sites in the basin.

Vertical gaps in the Pareto-frontier are associated with the addition of major dams. The Pareto front is thus composed of multiple filaments. Each filament differs from the one directly above by the inclusion of a single new mainstream reservoir, located directly downstream of the one already present in the above filament (see arrows and labels in Figure 2a). Within the same filament, the portfolios differ from one another by the inclusion of smaller dams on the tributaries.

Figure 2b shows the spatial layout of the four portfolios in the objective space. Portfolio I is an example of a low production-low trapping-low emission solution. Large dams are constructed only on the Upper MRB, while smaller projects are included in the upper part of already-dammed tributaries. Portfolio II greatly increases the energy generation compared to I with little impact on sediment. The reason for that is that most dams added between I and II are projects in China that are located upstream of existing dams. Nonetheless, II leads also to a major increase in GHG emissions (I: 13.6 Tg CO₂ eq/yr, II: 17.2 Tg CO₂ eq/yr). Portfolio III presents an alternative to II, with much lower sediment delivery but a smaller GHG footprint. Portfolio II includes numerous smaller dams on the tributaries while leaving the mainstream mostly connected, except for the reservoirs in the Upper MRB and a reservoir (the Mekong-Sanakham) in the Lower MRB that would only partially dam the channel, thus trapping only a minimal fraction of the incoming sediment load. On the contrary, portfolio III includes three large mainstream reservoirs (Pakbeng, Luangprabang, and Paklay), while including fewer small reservoirs on the tributaries. Finally, portfolio IV is an example of a solution with high hydropower production solution, with all planned major mainstream reservoirs including the Sambor reservoir. Finally, portfolio IV showcases an extremely hydropower-focused portfolio that includes all planned mainstream reservoirs, including the Sambor dam.

4.2. Robustness Analysis

For each dam, we analyze how likely it is to be included in Pareto-optimal portfolios above a certain hydropower generation (Ziv et al., 2012). This can serve as an indicator for when (i.e., which hydropower demand) a project might become a strategic choice for development. For instance, if a dam is included in 90% of portfolios above 130,000 GWh/yr (current generation) then it likely presents a strategic option to expand hydropower in the near future. If it is only included in 10% of portfolios above 260,000 GWh/yr, then it presents likely a poor choice even for high levels of hydropower demand.

We also study those probability metrics over the 5120 optimization runs, to explore the effects of uncertainty on the results. For instance, we can analyze how much the generation with which a dam is included in 90% of portfolios varies across the optimization runs. If that range is small, uncertainty is small, and the information on the competitiveness of the dam project is robust to uncertainty.

The shade of gray in Figure 3a indicates with which probability a dam is included in hydropower portfolios above a certain generation. Results indicate that mainstream dams tend to be included less often the more downstream they are located. Projects on the lower Mekong tributaries are only included for very high levels of hydropower generation.

Figure 3b shows the variation of the >90% probability of inclusion threshold across the same selected projects. This parameter gives an indication of how uncertainty affects strategic decisions for which dams to include for different levels of hydropower generation. For most mainstream dams on the Mekong, this variability is low and we can thus make robust recommendations at which level of generation a dam becomes a strategic choice. While

Figure 2. Optimizing dam portfolios for the least impact on sediment and least greenhouse gas emissions highlights conflicts between environmental objectives. Points in (a) represent tradeoffs between hydropower (x-axis), sediment (y-axis), and greenhouse gas emissions (color) for PO portfolios. Black dotted arrows near axes labels indicate the preferred direction of each objective. Note that the objective also accounts for the trapping potential, emissions, and energy generation of already existing or in-construction projects. Names on the Pareto front indicate the inclusion of major dams in PO dam portfolios, which leads to major shifts in objectives (see inset for dam locations). Note that portfolios associated with the best trade-offs between sediment and energy (on the top margin of the frontier) present the highest GHG emissions (red). Roman numerals I–IV indicate portfolios that are discussed throughout the text. (b) Shows the layout for portfolios I–IV.

the uncertainty is greater for upper Mekong dams, there is no overlap between uncertainty ranges for upper and lower Mekong dams. Thus, prioritizing the upper Mekong dams at lower levels of generation is a more strategic choice to improve trade-offs among the three considered objectives. Our analysis also indicates with high

confidence (i.e., low variability in Figure 3b box plots) that dams on the lower Mekong tributaries are “last resorts,” and are included only for very high levels of generation. Notable exceptions to this poor performance of lower Mekong tributary dams are Lower Se San 1 and Xe Kong 3S, for which however uncertainty is amongst the greatest of all considered dams.

Our analysis can be readily expanded to all Mekong dams. Figure 4 shows for which generation level dams are included in at least 90% of portfolios. Green colors indicate dams that are included for lower levels of hydropower generation. For instance, nearly all dams on the upper Mekong (Figure 4a) are frequently included in portfolios with 135,000–175,000 GWh/yr, making them strategic choices for a near-term expansion of hydropower from the current level. In contrast, most tributary dams are included only for levels of generation that represent a major expansion over the current status quo (240,000 GWh/yr, blue/purple colors). Dams on the mainstream of the lower Mekong are included mostly above 200,000 GWh/yr. Finally, Figure 4 also indicates the robustness of our results. Larger icons with thicker outlines indicate dams for which uncertainty is greater. Notably, smaller tributary dams are subject to a higher level of uncertainty in their probability of inclusion (Figures 4b and 4c).

5. Discussion

Our findings advance strategic planning about future hydropower accounting for multiple objectives and decision variables, as well as large uncertainty in environmental data. Our results build upon and expand previous studies from Ziv et al. (2012), Schmitt, Bizzi, et al. (2019), Schmitt et al. (2018a), Flecker et al. (2022), and Almeida et al. (2019). Notably, our approach includes objectives for more local/regional (sediment) and global (greenhouse gas emissions) and introduces generalizable metrics for assessing uncertainty.

Pareto-optimal portfolios highlight trade-offs between multiple environmental objectives (Figure 2), similar to findings by Flecker et al. (2022) for the Amazon. Notably, portfolios that are optimal from a sediment perspective tend to emit more GHG, as they favor the construction of many smaller reservoirs on tributaries whose cumulative emissions tend to surpass the alternative large mainstream projects with equivalent production. However, this conflict is only present for portfolios with intermediate levels of hydropower generation, as portfolios with higher hydropower production are unequivocally harmful to both the sediment delivery and GHG emission objectives, as evidenced by the reduced thickness of the Pareto front for higher cumulative hydropower production values (Figure 2a). Reservoir projects on the lower Mekong tributaries tend to combine significant GHG emissions with high sediment trapping, both correlated to large flooded areas, and thus present poor choices for development. In general, however, the conflict between environmental objectives is less pronounced than between this objective and the cumulative hydropower production, as including more dams inevitably negatively affects both sediment connectivity and GHG emissions.

Another novelty in our research is the consideration of uncertainty, particularly when it comes to sediment management in dams. Considering sediment management is crucial to realistically represent the cumulative impacts of dams on sediment. Yet, including sediment management is also challenging and uncertain, because its effectiveness will depend on many dam-specific factors that are usually only determined when projects are in more advanced stages of planning and design, which generally occurs after the period in which strategic planning is usually implemented.

Repeating the strategic optimization for thousands of different input states allows evaluation of the robustness of strategic planning approaches under uncertainty. For instance, the likelihood of a dam being included in an optimal portfolio for a certain generation can yield insights for when its development might be optimal (i.e., least impact, greatest benefit option) (Flecker et al., 2022; Ziv et al., 2012) (Figure 3). Evaluating this metric for each dam over the many independent optimizations allows the identification of dams for which uncertainty hampers the ability to make strategic decisions. For instance, our results indicate that there is some uncertainty around which dams in the upper Mekong would be strategic near-term choices. Yet, there is very little uncertainty around the fact that those dams are much more strategic to build than dams in the lower Mekong mainstream and its tributaries, at least given the configurations of dams already constructed in the basin. Small projects on still undammed tributaries, like the Tonle Sap basin and the lower 3S basin, are never prioritized.

The results presented in this paper are dependent on the presence of already-built dams in the MRB, and may change when considering a pristine basin without any pre-existing infrastructures. Schmitt et al. (2018a) searched for optimal development strategies for the pristine basin considering sediment connectivity and energy production

Figure 3. Supporting robust decisions for multi-objective strategic siting of the largest mainstream dams in the Mekong and 3S river system. How often dams are included in PO portfolios indicates which dams are more advantageous to build for different levels of hydropower demand (Ziv et al., 2012), according to the criteria used in the analysis. Colors (in scale of gray) indicate average inclusion probability over 5120 optimization runs, as an indicator of which dams result in less severe trade-offs for near-future development. The green, red and blue stars denote the hydropower demand for which a specific dam project is included in >10%, >50%, and >90% of PO portfolios. The boxplots in (b) show how the position of the minimum 90% inclusion indicator (blue star in figure a) varies over 5120 optimization runs, highlighting how uncertainty affects the attractiveness of each project. (c) Shows the location of dams in the basin.

Figure 4.

and found that even in this case reservoirs on the upper MRB remained prime candidates for early development, while dam development on the main channel in the middle and lower MRB was strongly discouraged. However, results may change when considering new objectives like GHGs emission reduction.

In future studies, there is potential to expand on this research by including additional objectives in strategic planning under uncertainty and improving upon the estimates of uncertainty for the already considered objectives. If more parameters for each dam were available, sediment management strategies could be modeled in a more detailed fashion. Basin-scale hydrological models could be adopted to calculate the effect of upstream reservoir management operations on the hydropower production of each dam, used in Equation 2, and to elaborate an integrated management strategy. As variability in hydropower operation can also have a significant impact on downstream emission rates (Calamita et al., 2021), these could include strategies specifically tailored towards reducing GHG emissions via water and sediment management in the reservoirs or across the catchment.

Additional environmental objectives that could be introduced for the Mekong are discussed, for example, in Flecker et al. (2022), which considers degrees of hydrological alteration, river network connectivity, and fish biodiversity threat. Social impacts, such as forced displacement of local communities, could also be accounted. Moreover, while reservoirs on the Mekong are primarily built for hydropower production, they may fulfill secondary purposes, like flood protection and water storage for industrial or agricultural uses, that could be included in the analysis.

Moreover, the study does not consider that a dam GHG emissions factor and its upstream sediment supply are often intertwined. For instance, the construction of dams upstream can lead to a decrease in the delivery of sediment to the reservoir. This, in turn, can reduce the rate of remineralization and decomposition, which contribute to the emissions of greenhouse gases. Therefore, the rate of GHG emissions from a dam may vary depending upon its portfolio configurations. However, more research is needed to determine the exact impact of this relationship on each reservoir.

Another important addition would also be to include uncertainty in the generation, which might change significantly compared to Schmitt, Bizzi, et al. (2019) and Schmitt, Kittner, et al. (2019) central estimates used in this study because of climate change, the emergence of alternative sources of renewable energy (Opperman et al., 2019; Schmitt, Kittner, et al., 2019), and operation of upstream reservoirs. Results obtained using a larger suite of objectives, uncertainties, and indicators may shift the ranking described in this paper, and return a different optimal dam build sequence.

To conclude, this study presents for the first time how strategic decision analysis can robustly inform hydropower planning in large and poorly monitored river basins. Strategic planning tends to be most effective in the early stages of hydropower development. In many parts of the world, this implies operating in river systems about which very little is known. Herein we demonstrate that even limited information, which would be similarly available for most rivers worldwide, allows us to robustly identify dam portfolios that result in better trade-offs between conflicting energy and environmental objectives. Notably, this approach also highlights the uncertainty associated with ranking each project, and indicates which type of information and for which parts of the basin result in a further increase in the robustness of the result. We thus suggest that our results can be useful to inform policy debates and decisions around sustainable hydropower development in the Mekong and elsewhere.

6. Conclusions

Planning large hydropower development projects by employing an integrated, multi-objective perspective can help identify more sustainable configurations than the one achieved from project-by-project planning. While the latter has been the predominant approach used for the construction of large reservoirs until now, it is becoming increasingly clear that the resulting configurations would be severely detrimental to the social, economic, and

Figure 4. Visualization of the location, hydropower generation, lowest production threshold for inclusion, and the relative uncertainty, for all planned dams on the Mekong. The figure shows the planned dams on the Mekong, using different markers to distinguish dam hydropower generation. The color in each marker denotes the lowest cumulative hydropower production of the PO portfolios in which the dams are present >90% of the time. Marker border thickness indicates the standard deviation of >90% probability threshold. Panels (a–c) show details of the map for the Upper MRB, the Lower MRB highlands, and the lowland portion and 3S system respectively.

ecological conditions of the river, and could also result in the emission of large quantities of GHG from previously considered green sources.

On the Mekong River Basin, the results of our research give insights into a possible optimal sequencing of dam construction considering sediments and GHG as environmental objectives. The completion of projects located in the upper basin and upstream of already dammed tributaries should be prioritized in the early stages of future hydropower development since they have the least negative effects on both sediment delivery and GHG emissions. If needed, further development should prioritize building dams from upstream to downstream, starting with the highlands south of the Chinese border. Dams on the Tonle Sap Basin and the mainstream Mekong near the delta should be discarded unless we seek to tap all the remaining hydropower potential. These conclusions appear robust despite the deep uncertainties in the estimation of the indicators for sediment connectivity disruption and GHG emissions for such a large-scale and data-scarce case study. These uncertainties only affect the ranking of smaller reservoirs, particularly in the 3S river basin.

Hydropower development is now proceeding at a fast pace, primarily in emerging economies of Southeast Asia, South America, and Africa, due to the need to match rising energy demands without relying on carbon-intensive sources. The approach used in this paper, eventually expanded by including additional economic, social, and environmental indicators and more refined modeling tools, demonstrate the benefits of an exploratory, early development screening tool to select optimal and robust development portfolios even in data-scarce environments. The information obtained by the initial screening of viable portfolios via the presented approach can then guide new research to quantify with more precision the portfolio performances using more computationally intensive approaches (like dynamic reservoir operations designs and physics-based models of river and delta morphological response to alterations), or to arrange new data collection campaigns, in order to support decision-makers in identifying optimal sustainable development options.

Data Availability Statement

The data and codes used in this paper are available in Tangi et al. (2024).

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